

Acid-Catalyzed Dissociation of Cobalt(III) Chelates I. Aquation Kinetics of *Cis*-Diaquobisbiguanidecobalt(III) Perchlorate

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The kinetics of the acid-catalyzed dissociation of *cis*-diaquobisbiguanidecobalt(III) complex ion was made spectrophotometrically in the temperature range 50°-65° in presence of 0.3 to 2.0 M perchloric acid. The second order rate constants (k') at various temperatures were evaluated from the slopes of the lines obtained by plotting k_{obs} vs $[\text{HClO}_4]$. The enthalpy and entropy of activations were determined in the usual manner and the values were found to be $\Delta H^\ddagger = 15.2 \pm 0.7$ k cal mol⁻¹ and $\Delta S^\ddagger = -31.6 \pm 2.1$ e.u. Kinetically the *bis*-complex is more stable than its *trans*-analogue. A dissociation mechanism was proposed for the aquation reaction.

STEPWISE dissociation of cobalt(III)-biguanide complex in acid solution is well established¹. *Tris*-biguanidecobalt(III) complex ion aquates² at a measurable rate in acid solution with the formation of diaquobisbiguanide complex. This diaquo-complex further dissociate to tetraaquomonobiguanide complex and spontaneously decomposes to cobaltous ion with simultaneous release of biguanides. In this paper, the dissociation of diaquobisbiguanidecobalt(III) ion to tetraaquomonobiguanidecobalt(III) ion in aqueous acidic medium is reported as a function of acid concentration, ionic strength and temperature.

Experimental

Materials and reagents :

Diaquobisbiguanidecobalt(III) perchlorate—Hydroxoquoobisbiguanidecobalt(III) sulphate was prepared by the method of Ray and Ghosh³. Its purity was checked by analysis (Found : Co, 13.44 ; N, 32.60 per cent. Calcd, for $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]\text{SO}_4 \cdot 2.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Co, 13.50 ; N, 32.04 per cent.). A solution of the complex perchlorate was prepared before use by metatheses of the complex sulphate with an equivalent amount of barium perchlorate. It is known³ that the hydroxoquo-complex in aqueous solution forms an equilibrium mixture with the diaquo-complex. The pK value for the reaction $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{2+} + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightleftharpoons [\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2+} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ was determined at various temperatures (30° - 50°) by the pH titration of the complex perchlorate with perchloric acid as 6.02 at 2M ionic strength. So in the experimental acid concentrations (0.3M-2.0M), the complex ion exists entirely as the diaquo species. The formation

of the diaquo-species is also evident from the immediate shift in the absorption maxima of $\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{OH})^{2+}$ from 480 nm to 490-495 nm by the addition of acid to an aqueous solutions of the latter. The absorption spectrum of the complex ion in 1M perchloric acid is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of 0.001 M solution of Diaquobisbiguanidecobalt(III) ion in presence of 1M perchloric acid (absorbance/cm)

Kinetic measurements :

The rates of reactions were followed spectrophotometrically in the same way as had been done with *trans*-dicyanobisbiguanidecobalt(III) ion⁴. The absorbance measurements were made at 490 nm,

corresponding to the absorption peak of the diaquo-complex, where a maximum change in absorption occurs. The rates were evaluated by Guggenhiems' plot⁵, as it was difficult to ascertain the absorption due to pure tetraaquo-complex.

Results and Discussion

The observed rate of dissociation of the complex ion at various complex and acid concentrations and different temperatures are reported in Table 1. The

TABLE-1

OBSERVED RATES FOR THE ACID-CATALYZED DISSOCIATION OF DIAQUOBISBIGUANIDECOBALT(III) PERCHLORATE AT VARIOUS ACID CONCENTRATIONS AND TEMPERATURE, $\mu=2.0M$

Complex $\times 10^{-3}M$	$HClO_4, M$	$10^3 k_{obsd} \text{ min}^{-1}$		
		55°	60°	65°
1	0.3		2.16	
2	0.3		2.21	
3	0.3		2.17	
1	0.5	2.10	2.90	4.34
1	0.7	3.78	5.16	6.14
1	1.0	4.90	6.90	9.01
1	1.2	5.00	8.44	
1	1.5		10.60	
1	2.0		12.50	
$10^3 k' \text{ min}^{-1}$ (second order rate constant)		4.8	6.95	8.95
$10^3 k' \text{ sec}^{-1}$ „ „		7.2	10.16	10.49

$$\Delta H^\ddagger = 15.2 \pm 0.7 \text{ k calories mol}^{-1} \quad \Delta S^\ddagger = -31.6 \pm 2.1 \text{ e.u.}$$

values given in the table are average of two or three individual runs and the rates are reproducible within three per cent. The rate of dissociation of the diaquo-complex remains unchanged with different initial amounts, indicating a first order dependence of rate on complex concentration. k_{obsd} changes with acid concentration. Plot of k_{obsd} vs $[HClO_4]$ (Figure 2) at various temperatures are straight lines with

Fig. 2. Effect of acid concentration on the rate of dissociation of Diaquobisbiguanidecobalt(III) ion at various temperatures ($\mu, 2$)
I— 55° ; II— 60° ; III— 65° .

zero intercept on ordinate. This indicates that the dissociation of the complex proceeds only through an acid-catalyzed path with virtually no contribution by any acid independent path. The straight line plot also indicates first order dependence of rate on acid concentration. From the slopes of these plots, the second order rate constant, k' , for the dissociation of the complex at various temperatures were determined and are also reported in Table 1. Corresponding theoretical rate law may be derived as :

$$-\frac{d}{dt} \ln [Co(BigH)_2(H_2O)_2^{3+}] = k_{obsd} = k'[H^+] \quad \dots(1)$$

Based on the above rate law, the mechanistic path of the dissociation may be given as :

The equilibrium constant ' K ' is assumed to be small, so that the concentration of the conjugate acid at any time is very small in comparison with the complex. Protonation takes place at the free basic= NH group of the cobalt bound biguanide molecule.

The effect of ionic strength on the rate is shown in Table 2. Rate increases but little with ionic

TABLE-2

EFFECT OF IONIC CONCENTRATION AND PERCHLORATE CONCENTRATION ON THE RATE OF DISSOCIATION OF DIAQUOBISBIGUANIDECOBALT(III) ION

Complex	Temp. 60°			μ	$[ClO_4^-]$	$10^3 k_{obs} \text{ min}^{-1}$
	$HClO_4, M$	$NaClO_4, M$	$Ba(ClO_4)_2, M$			
1	1.0	1.0		2.0	2.0	6.91
2	1.0	0.5		1.5	1.5	5.70
3	1.0			1.0	1.0	4.74
4	1.0		0.66	2.0	2.32	6.72

strength. Whether the rate increases with ionic strength or perchlorate concentration, was tested by using mixtures of sodium and barium perchlorates for maintaining different ionic and perchlorate concentrations. No remarkable effect of perchlorate concentration on the rate was observed, although the rate increases with ionic concentration.

The heat, ΔH^\ddagger and entropy, ΔS^\ddagger of activation for the second order rate constant, k' , were evaluated by making use of the Eyring

equation, $\log \frac{k'h}{KT} = \frac{\Delta S^\ddagger}{4.6} - \frac{\Delta H^\ddagger}{4.6T}$ (Figure 3) where ' h ' is

Planck's constant, ' K ' is the Boltzmann constant

and ' k ' is the second order rate constant for the dissociation of the complex ion. The ΔH^\ddagger value thus obtained is 15.2 ± 0.7 k cal mol⁻¹ and $\Delta S^\ddagger = -31.6 \pm 2.1$ e.u. ΔH^\ddagger for the dissociation of the bisbiguanide complex is higher than the corresponding value of the trisbiguanidecobalt(III) ion², indicating that the biscomplex is kinetically more stable than the tris-complex. This is a general behaviour observed with other biguanide complexes². The thermodynamic stability of the bis-complex is also much higher than the tris-complex showing stronger bonding in the previous one.

Fig. 3. Eyring plot for the dissociation of Diaquobisbiguanidecobalt(III) complex.

In the case of ligands which are better coordinated than water, the replacement of the ligand (in this experiment, it is biguanide) by water increases the effective positive charge on the metal atom due to weaker donation of electrons from the aquo ligand, compared to that from the ligand being replaced. The rupture of the cobalt-biguanide bond becomes increasingly difficult with increase in the effective positive charge on the cobalt atom and hence the decrease in rate occurs as observed with aquo complexes. As for example, it may be cited that while the tris-biguanidecobalt(III) perchlorate dissociates at a measurable rate ($48 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ at 27°) at room temperature in presence of 0.1M

HClO₄, the diaquobisbiguanide complex is almost stable at room temperature even in presence of 1M perchloric acid.

In this connection it may also be mentioned that Co(en)₂(H₂O)₂³⁺ and Co(mal)₂(H₂O)₂⁻, (where en = ethylenediamine, and mal = malonate) are much more reactive than their tris-analogues. Coen₃³⁺ is perfectly stable at 80° in presence of 1M perchloric acid but Coen₂(H₂O)₂³⁺ reacts at a measurable rate ($k = 1.5 \times 10^{-10} \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$) under the same conditions. Also while Co(mal)₃³⁻ reacts at a measurable rate at 25° and 0.1M HClO₄, Co(mal)₂(H₂O)₂⁻ is extremely labile under the same conditions⁷. In cobalt(III)-biguanide complexes, the observed opposite trend indicated by the greater reactivity of the tris-complex, indicates a different mechanism altogether. While in the former complexes, 'bond breaking' and 'bond making' by the incoming aquo ligands are both important in the transition state^{6,7}, in biguanide complexes it seems that 'bond breaking' is only important. The entropies of activation of tris- ($\Delta S^\ddagger = -31.5$ e.u.)² and bis- ($\Delta S^\ddagger = -31.6$ e.u.) complexes are almost equal indicating similar mechanisms operate in the aquation of both complex.

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